

IoT-based Peat Soil Heat Conduction Parameter Delivery System As Land Fire Mitigation Effort

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Abstract— Mitigating peatland fires needs to be done because the handling is more complex than ordinary land fires because of the fire spread in the layers below its surface. One of the efforts is to create an IoT-based data parameter of peat heat conduction sending system that integrates with information systems using web technology. Some conduction parameter data is generated by a multisensory system delivered on IoT devices that use the raspberry pi as client-side. The data is transmitted to cloud hosting to be displayed in real-time on the Web as server-side. The interface software on both sides used PHP and MySQL scripts. This system can send 14 data on the conduction parameters of peat soil samples, consisting of seven sample temperature points, one heater temperature, four sample water content points, air temperature, and surface air humidity of samples. Then all these parameters are saved and displayed on the Web in real-time.

Keywords—component; delivery; IoT; mitigation; peatland fires; Raspberry Pi;

I. INTRODUCTION

Peat soil has good potential in agriculture, but several obstacles cause low productivity. The characteristics of peat soils are very distinctive. Namely, they are easy to dry, do not turn over, and experience subsidence under aerobic conditions. Irreversible dry conditions make peat soil repel water on its surface, so water cannot enter the lower layer of peat[1].

The observation system that has been done only on vegetation above the surface using GIS (Geographic Information System) has not reached the peat layer below the surface. To determine the temperature of peat when approaching burning in the soil from the surface required the value of peat heat conductance so that the characterization of peat soil heat conductance is expected to provide data on the relationship between the heat temperature in the peat soil and the heat temperature at the peat soil surface. In the first stage in determining the heat conduction of peat soil, it is necessary to measure several parameters, including temperature and water

content of peat soil by a multisensory system, then proceed with further data processing.

Peatland fire mitigation efforts are carried out by monitoring the main indicators of peat fire triggers, namely peat temperature below the surface and surface of the land, groundwater content, air temperature, and surface air humidity, and can be observed in real-time. This article is discussed one of the systems to deliver data parameters of peat soil heat conduction based on IoT integrated with the information system on the website.

A. The Multisensor System

In situ measurement of thermal properties of a northern peatland had been done to make a temperature model with dual-probe heat pulse sensors and triple-probe heat pulse sensors [2]. This measurement gives the idea of making a multisensory system. It shown in Fig. 1 has been developed to measure in situ several parameters of peat soil samples placed in a chamber with a height of 0.5 m. The first parameter is peat soil moisture content, consisting of 4 soil moisture sensors arranged vertically in the chamber[3]. Then the next parameter is the temperature of the peat soil, which is measured by eight sensors in total. Seven of which are used to measure the temperature of 7 depth points of the peat soil sample arranged vertically in the chamber and a temperature sensor to measure the temperature of the heater placed at the bottom of the room. In addition, the system is also equipped with measuring environmental conditions around the sample, which consists of air temperature and humidity. The explanation of code sensors and chamber in Fig. 1 is written in Table 1.

B. Raspberry Pi

Raspberry Pi, shortened to RPi, is like a computer system with a complete I/O for computer support equipment, such as USB port, HDMI port, ethernet, wifi, and so on [4]. A very useful feature of the RPi that strongly supports this research is General Purpose Input Output (GPIO). The GPIO supports doing the interface with other equipment connected with RPi.

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(a) Hardware (b) Sensors and chamber

Fig. 1 System multisensory

Table 1 SENSOR CODE

No.	Code	Sensor Type
1	St1	Heater temperature1
2	St2	Soil temperature2
3	St3	Soil temperature3
4	St4	Soil temperature4
5	St5	Soil temperature5
6	St6	Soil temperature6
7	St7	Soil temperature7
8	St8	Soil temperature8
9	Su9	Air temperature
10	Ku10	Air humidity
11	Kt11	Soil moisture 1
12	Kt12	Soil moisture 2
13	Kt13	Soil moisture 3
14	Kt14	Soil moisture 4

Fig. 2 Raspberry Pi [5]

Specification of RPi shown in Fig. 2 is The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ is the final revision in the Raspberry Pi 3, integrated with Broadcom BCM2837B0. The processor is Cortex-A53 (ARMv8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.4GHz, 1GB LPDDR2 SDRAM, 2.4GHz and 5GHz IEEE 802.11.b/g/n/ac wireless LAN, the wireless communication using Bluetooth 4.2, BLE Gigabit Ethernet over USB 2.0 (maximum throughput 300 Mbps), extended 40-pin GPIO header, and Full-size HDMI[5]. This device can be applied for general purposes.

The application of RPi as the main unit of a particular system has begun to be thought of because it can be used as the main device faster than a microcontroller even though the I/O device is limited. One of which is used to make decisions for three detection levels for drunk drivers[6]. The other is exposed to various cybercriminals and protects data [7], then monitors temperature[8].

C. IoT

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a set of heterogeneous connected devices that collaborate with the internet of services via the global network infrastructure [9]. IoT Application domains focus on nine domains: smart manufacturing or industrial, smart transportation/mobility, smart grid/energy, smart retail, smart cities, smart healthcare, smart supply chain, smart agriculture, and smart building/home[10], and IoT security issues emphasis on availability, authenticity, confidentiality, integrity, non-repudiation, and privacy[9]. The IoT applied here prefers smart agriculture, especially in disaster management.

D. Information System based on Web

Web-based technology is one of information and communication technology applications. The development of web technology is very fast, with both related devices and software-hardware devices associated with it.[11]

Web data framework, or web-based data framework, employs Web innovations to provide data and administrations to clients or other data systems/applications. It may be a code whose fundamental reason is to distribute and keep up information by utilizing hypertext-based standards [12]. A web data system usually comprises one or more web applications, particular functionality-oriented components, besides data components and other non-web components. The web browser is regularly utilized as front-end while the database is back-end.

The development of WBIS (web-based information system) is required a server with services like Web Server, Database Services, Messaging Services, Mailing Services, and Collaboration Services [13].

II. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The data of peat heat conduction sending systems are composed of IoT devices and web-based information systems. To apply this, then in simple term shown in Fig. 3. The multisensory system is connected to the IoT device via wireless media, and then the data is sent to the information system on the Web. In this article, the multisensory systems will not be discussed further.

Fig. 3 The general block system

The IoT device is developed with RPi 3, module wireless nRF24101, and modem. It is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 The IoT device

The main device of IoT is RPi. RPi manages the interface of the nRF24101 module so that the received wirelessly transmitted peat conduction parameter data can be read and processed in the RPi. and then sent to a web-based information system via a modem using an internet connection.

III. SOFTWARE TOOLS

A. Delivery IoT System

The IoT system uses a special algorithm to work. RPi uses the Raspbian operating system, then installs Thonny, Python IDE for beginners with many features, including a focus on Python and has an interactive environment[14][15], to interface with the system multisensory through GPIO connected to the nRF24101 module. The special algorithm to receive data from the system multisensory is shown in Fig. 5. And then, the data is delivered to system information with PHP, a popular general-purpose scripting language that is especially suited to web development[16].

Fig. 5 Flowchart receiving data from system multisensory

B. System Information

Some of the software used to develop the system in this study uses CodeIgniter (CI) as Framework[17] with Domain

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Name is <http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/>. It is hosted on Cloud Hosting by Rumahweb Indonesia. In general, an outline of how this software works is presented in Fig. 6:

Fig. 6 Software works

To gather data from the sensor, we create the HTTP request catcher, where the sensor through RPi sends data as HTTP URL access with several data parameters. The parameters are automatically inserted into the database on the cloud hosting. Then Web-Based Information is processing text data into charts and graphics that can be seen on <http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/>.

C. Interface System IoT and System information

In most RPi projects, sending data to a website (or in the website's database) is very crucial. If we want to access the room's sensor and consumption data in our devices through a website in real-time, we must first transfer data from the IoT device to the website. The algorithm to transfer data is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Flowchart interface of system IoT and system information

On the client-side (RPi), we make an HTTP(s) request to the server sending the data as request parameters using URL every two minutes using this code.

```

pload = {'sens1':(s1), 'sens2':(s2), 'sens3':(s3), 'sens4':(s4),
        'sens5':(s5), 'sens6':(s6), 'sens7':(s7), 'sens8':(s8),
        'sens9':(s9), 'sens10':(k10), 'sens11':(k11),
        'sens12':(k12), 'sens13':(k13), 'sens14':(k14)}
if (int(round(time.time()*1000)) - last_time >= time_interval*60000):
    print(datetime.now().strftime("%H:%M:%S"))
    last_time = int(round(time.time()*1000))

try:
    print('hostname = ' is up!')
    r = requests.Session().post
    |'http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/sensorbaru/sensor.php', data = pload, timeout = 5)
except:
    traceback.print_exc()
    print(datetime.now().strftime("%H:%M:%S"))
    
```

Fig. 8 Code of interface in client-side

The output URL on Fig. 8 will look like this :

<http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/sensorbaru/sensor.php?sens1=val1&sens2=val2&sens3=val3&sens4=val4&sens5=val5&sens6=val6&sens7=val7&sens8=val8&sens9=val9&sens10=val10&sens11=val11&sens12=val12&sens13=val13&sens14=val14>

On the server-side, the HTTP server runs a small PHP script sensor.php for each such request which receives the data, makes some plausibility checks (and possibly authentication), and then stores the data into the database. Sensor.php will receive 14 values as sens1, sens2, sens3 until sens14 then convert it to MySQL value for insert into database. This small PHP script is shown in Fig. 9.

```

@sens1 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens1']);
@sens2 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens2']);
@sens3 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens3']);
@sens4 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens4']);
@sens5 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens5']);
@sens6 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens6']);
@sens7 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens7']);
@sens8 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens8']);
@sens9 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens9']);
@sens10 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens10']);
@sens11 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens11']);
@sens12 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens12']);
@sens13 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens13']);
@sens14 = mysqli_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens14']);
    
```

Fig. 9 Code of interface in server-side

The web interface on <http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/> contains some information that shows sensor data like air temperature, land temperature, air humidity, and land humidity in the chart shown in Fig. 10, Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Fig. 13.

Fig. 10 Graph time series of seven-point soil and heater temperatures

Fig. 11 Graph time series of four-point soil moisture

Fig. 12 Graph time series of air temperature

Fig. 13 Graph time series of air humidity

And the history of data is also shown in Fig. 14 at the bottom of the page.

Fig. 14 Time series of historical data on master-side

IV. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

After IoT device and system information are integrated, the heat conduction parameter of peat soil measurement is ready to be implemented. The process implementing system started with sampling data peat soil. The sampling location is at Banua Hanyar Village, Batumandi District, Balangan Regency, in South Kalimantan - Indonesia. The sampling process and peat soil appearance are presented in Fig. 15. Samples were taken from the surface to a depth of 50 cm and put into a container with the same depth position as the point where the sample was taken.

Fig. 15 Sampling peat soil

Second, the implementation system is the main function process that delivers and receives the data measurement from the multisensory system. This process is shown in Fig. 16. The sample is put in a container in the multisensory system, and then some data is measured. It is sent wirelessly to the IoT device. Then the IoT device receives it and then sends it back to the server to be saved and displayed on a web-based information system.

Fig. 16 Process in situ measurement sample parameters of heat conduction

Third, the sample measurement is displayed on a Web-based information system, and they are presented in Fig. 10, Fig. 11, Fig. 12, Fig. 13., and Fig. 14. To see the data more clearly the condition when the data was measured. Each data point can be marked using the mouse by using a left click on the data point in question, and then a legend of the measurement time and its value will be displayed near the data point, then presented in Fig. 17. Integrating IoT devices and Web-based information systems in real-time and historical data from smart objects have been discussed[18].

The data measurement is further analyzed to determine the heat conduction. The data is plotted again to find a special condition with a small fluctuation temperature for a long time. From this condition temperature of two points, the heat conduction of soil peat was determined. One of the plot graphs is shown in Fig. 18. Based on the graph, it can be seen that the system can run for approximately 8,500 minutes without stopping.

Fig. 17 The data point measurement

Fig. 18 Analyze data in chart

Several events can be a concern in the measurement process when implementing the system. The first is that the internet quota used in the modem cannot be used up because there is no relationship between the IoT device and the server. And the data is never stored in the IoT device nor displayed. So in the future, the bandwidth of the internet to send data need to be managed[19].

The second is to restart the IoT device if the first condition reconnected to the server. So it is necessary to use a warning system to the administrator if both conditions occur. For the future, a data security system must be developed and implemented[20].

The three stages of system implementation have been carried out with good results, especially for the second and the third. So the delivery system parameter of heat conduction peat soil IoT-based as land fire mitigation can be used to measure the conduction parameters of peat soils with varying peat samples.

V. CONCLUSION

The delivery system parameter of heat conduction peat soil based on IoT can work well. The system consists of two main parts: IoT devices and web-based information systems. In its implementation, the system can run for approximately 8,500 minutes without stopping, and data can be displayed and stored on the server properly.

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